

Temporal Structures and Colonial Tensions: A Genettean Reading of *Things Fall Apart*, *Arrow of God*, and *No Longer at Ease*

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the interplay between narrative temporality and colonial tensions in Chinua Achebe's *Things Fall Apart*, *Arrow of God*, and *No Longer at Ease* through the lens of Gérard Genette's narratology. By focusing on Genette's categories of order, duration, frequency, and narrative voice, the study demonstrates how Achebe's temporal structures embody the disjunctures and conflicts of the colonial encounter. Shifts in chronology, oscillations between repetition and singularity, and variations in narrative perspective not only shape the reader's experience of time but also mirror the destabilizing effects of colonial domination and cultural negotiation. The article argues that Genettean temporal analysis, when placed in dialogue with postcolonial critique, reveals how Achebe's novels resist linear, Eurocentric historiographies by inscribing fractured, plural, and contested experiences of time. In doing so, the study highlights the narratological dimension of Achebe's project of cultural recovery and its broader implications for rethinking the relationship between narrative form and colonial history

1. Introduction

Narrative theory or *Narratology* is a literary theory concerned with "the study of the form and functioning of narrative" (Prince 4). Hans Bertens explains that narratology aims at identifying "a general model of narration that will cover all the possible ways in which stories can be told ..." (60). Gerard Genette's model of narratology, presented in his notable *Narrative Discourse: An Essay in Method* (1972) is "by general consensus the most influential of all structuralist studies" (Bertens 60). Genette suggests that there are three levels of narrative: story, narrative, and narration (27):

"Story provides the content of the tale in the order in which events 'actually happened' to the characters, an order that does not always coincide with the order in which they are presented in the narrative. Narrative refers to the actual words on the page, the discourse, the text itself, from which the reader constructs both story and narration ... Narration refers to the act of telling the story to some audience and thereby producing the narrative. (Tyson 228)"

Although Genette's theory focuses mainly on the narrative discourse, he insists that analyzing a literary text necessarily "implies a study of relationships" (Genette 27) among all three levels; story, narrative, and narration. To do that, Genette proposes three categories under which any given literary text could be examined: Tense, Mood, and Voice. Drawing on Genette's model this article focuses on the category of "Tense" in the three novels under consideration.

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2. Order

Achebe's first novel *Things Fall Apart* "opens by placing Okonkwo in the present, but immediately represents shifting time frames—we are taken back to the time when Okonkwo was eighteen, to the ancient founding of Umuofia, and back to the present again" (Gikandi, Reading Chinua 29-30). Achebe starts his story in regular order; introducing the central character, Okonkwo, to the reader. He then quickly goes back many years to tell his readers a minor story that illustrates why Okonkwo, is considered a great man despite his young age. Genette calls this discrepancy between "the order in which the events of the story occur in the fictional world ... [and] the order in which the narrative presents those events ... 'anachrony'" (Tyson 228). According to Genette, anachronies are either flashbacks - *analepsis*- or flash-forwards - *prolepsis*. Peter Barry states that:

“Typically, writers make strategic use of both analepsis and prolepsis in telling a story, for the beginning is seldom the best place to begin - stories tend to begin in the middle (in medias res, as the theorists of classical times said), with analeptic material sketching out what went before, and proleptic devices hinting at what the outcome will be, and thereby engaging the reader and generating the basic narrative momentum. (234)”

So, at the beginning of chapter one Achebe uses analepsis to tell the story of Amalinze the Cat; a story whose only significance is to demonstrate Okonkwo's ferocity and fearlessness: “As a young man of eighteen he had brought honor to his village by throwing Amalinze the Cat” (TFA 3; ch.1). Achebe uses the same narrative technique again in the first chapter to flashback on the life of Unoka, Okonkwo's father, who died years ago. Achebe dedicates nearly five pages of the six-page chapter to offer a panoramic view of Unoka's life just to reveal why Okonkwo “had had no patience with his father” (TFA 4; ch.1). By doing so, Achebe “foregrounds [Okonkwo's] heroic persona, portraying him as a symbolic embodiment of the values and ideals of his village” (Whittaker xi). Looking at the first chapter of *Things Fall Apart* the reader notices that Achebe dedicates the majority of the chapter to two analeptic narratives that support the characterization of Okonkwo which enables the writer to provide the readers with a quick, albeit adequate, introduction to the remaining bulk of his novel.

In the last paragraph in the first chapter Achebe utilizes ‘repeating prolepsis’ which describes a section in the narrative that “refers in advance to an event that will be told in full in its place” (Genette 73). Achebe employs this technique skillfully in the concluding sentence in chapter one to keep the reader curious about the story of the “ill-fated lad [who] was called Ikemefuna” (TFA 8; ch.1), who would later on be given to the village of Umuofia as a “prerequisite for peace” (Njeng, Achebe's Work 4) with a neighboring village. Again in chapter two Achebe jumps to the future using repeating prolepsis to tell his audience that Ikemefuna would live in Okonkwo's household for three years. This piece of information is provided for the audience before they know the specific details of how that boy in particular came to be given to Umuofia to avoid war. Later in the same chapter, Achebe narrates the full story using analepsis to take us back in time to the night when Mbaino elders went to Ikemefuna's house:

“As for the boy himself, he was terribly afraid. He could not understand what was happening to him or what he had done. How could he know that his father had taken a hand in killing a daughter of Umuofia? All he knew was that a few men had arrived at their house, conversing with his father in low tones, and at the end he had been taken out and handed over to a stranger. ... And so the stranger had brought him, and a girl, a long, long way from home, through lonely forest paths. (TFA 15; ch.2)”

In chapter three Achebe travels back in time to an incident in the life of Unoka, Okonkwo's father. The chapter starts with the following sentences: “Okonkwo did not have the start in life which many young men usually had. He did not inherit a barn from his father. There was no barn to inherit” (TFA 16; ch.3). Immediately after this introduction, the writer uses a narrative segment that explains why Okonkwo had such a destitute adulthood: “The story was told in Umuofia, of how his father, Unoka, had gone to consult the Oracle of the Hills and the Caves to find out why he always had a miserable harvest” (TFA 16; ch.3). Then Achebe goes on for three retrospective pages stating the lengthy story about the unsuccessful life of Okonkwo's father.

Although the second chapter conforms to the chronological order of the main storyline of Okonkwo, the bulk of the third chapter brings us back again when Okonkwo was still a young man trying to make an impressive start away from his unsuccessful father. Achebe resorts to analepsis to give his audience a background to Okonkwo's life and provide evidence of his bitter upbringing. Here Achebe narrates the story of how Okonkwo had to support his father's house besides his own family, while he was still young. Near the end of the chapter Achebe suddenly returns to the regular chronological order of the story, with Okonkwo reminiscing over that year “with a cold shiver throughout the rest of his life. It always surprised him when he thought of it later that he did not sink under the load of despair” (TFA 24; ch.3). So far, Achebe goes back and forth in time to let the reader inside Okonkwo's world to provide a detailed background to his life and personality; a background that the reader appreciates.

Prolepsis is used in chapter four when Achebe mentions Nwoye's relationship with Ikemefuna: “Nwoye remembered this period very vividly till the end of his life. He even remembered how he had laughed when Ikemefuna told him that the proper name for a corn cob with only a few scattered grains was *eze-agadi-nwayi*, or the teeth of an old woman” (TFA 34; ch. 4). This very brief leap to the future implies that Achebe has insight into the future life of Nwoye; and makes the reader curious to know what will become of both Nwoye and Ikemefuna in the future.

The story of the missionaries' first arrival to Igboland is narrated twice; both in analeptic mood. The first time the story of the white man's arrival to Abame village is mentioned in chapter fifteen, with much less detail than the second time in chapter sixteen where Achebe narrates the full story employing direct speech between the white man and the villagers. By so doing, Achebe dramatizes this part of the narrative and adds an audio/visual quality to the situation, hence creating a more vivid portrait of how the missionaries managed to win their first converts. Achebe tells us about how Nwoye, Okonkwo's son, came to join the white man's religion in a fairytale-like style:

“But there was a young lad who had been captivated. His name was Nwoye, Okonkwo's first son. It was not the mad logic of the Trinity that captivated him. ... The hymn about brothers who sat in darkness and in fear seemed to answer a vague and persistent question that haunted his young soul--the question of the twins crying in the bush and the question of Ikemefuna who was killed. (TFA 147; ch.16)”

Although the story of *Arrow of God* opens when Ezeulu's son is already a member of the new religion, it's in chapter four that Achebe informs his readers of the detailed story of how Oduche came to join the church in the first place. Achebe dedicates more

than six pages to offer an analeptic narrative section about the background story of why Oduche attempted to kill the royal python. Ezeulu “stood speechless” (AG 46 ch.4) because he could not imagine that his son would dare do such an abomination, although Oduche only dared to lock the python inside a box. Simon Gikandi maintains that Oduche has “the audacity to try and kill the royal python because he is now in a universe of meanings in which the python has no symbolic value” (Reading Chinua 69), a fact that Ezeulu fails to realize and refuses to acknowledge; because if he does he would be the only person to take the blame for the breakdown of the traditional order of Umuaro.

Achebe structures *No Longer at Ease* as a long analeptic narrative discourse that goes back in time to narrate the story of Obi Okonkwo, the protagonist. Except for the last few lines of the novel, the first two pages of the first chapter is the only part of the novel that conforms to the chronological order of the story. “The effect of the flashback is to concentrate attention on the causes for Obi’s conviction and the complexity of events, actions and decisions which lead up to it” (Killam 36). The story opens with the court scene where the reader is yet to discover what Obi has done to be awaiting trial. By choosing to open his novel with a prolepsis Achebe achieves a heightened *level of suspense* where the reader is anxious to find out “how a young man of [obi’s] education and brilliant promise could have done this” (NLE 4; ch.1).

In the fourth page of the first chapter Achebe travels back in time “six or seven years” to inform the reader of the short history of the Umuofia Progressive Union and its efforts in helping their country by sending “some of their brighter young men to study in England” (AG 7; ch.1). A few lines later Achebe goes back further using another analeptic summary of the early years of Obi’s boyhood to explain to the reader why “the selection of the first candidate had not presented any difficulty to the Union. Obi was an obvious choice” (AG 7; ch.1). Therefore, based on Genette’s model of narrative order, the first chapter corresponds to the following formula: A6-B5-C7-D2-E3-F1-G4; with letters representing the order of events as they appear in the narrative discourse and numbers representing the order of events in the narrated story (Figure 1).

Figure 1: NLE; ch.1.

The second chapter is another manifest example of Achebe’s tampering with the order of narrative. In a five-page chapter the narrative order shifts from one point to another then back to a previous point. The starting point of chapter two is a very brief summary of Obi’s years in England. The narrative then jumps to Obi’s return to Nigeria and how he was shocked to see a different Lagos than the one he imagined while he was away in England. Another jump to the past explains how Obi was fascinated with Lagos as a boy, with its “electric lights and motorcars” (NLE 10; ch.2). Thus, in the course of ten lines the narrative time shifts three times.

The third paragraph in the same chapter takes the reader to the day Obi was leaving Nigeria to England and his first visit to Lagos. The next section depicts Obi’s life with Clara in Lagos after his return from England. Here Obi’s thoughts interject with the current temporal framework and jumps back again to when Obi was in England; then back again to Obi’s life in Lagos. Thus, the formula that would correspond to the temporal relationships presented in this chapter is: A3-B4-C1-D2-E4-F3-G4 (Figure 2).

Figure 2: NLE; ch.2

The rest of the novel conforms to a great extent to the chronological order of Obi’s full story; starting from his long exhausting journey on the ship back from England, to the moment where he was arrested for taking a bribe. In the first two chapters of *No Longer at Ease* Achebe keeps going back and forth in this unconventional manner in the past years of Obi’s life to furnish the reader with a quick background to the life of the protagonist.

Considering the order of narrative in the two novels, one might conclude that *Things Fall Apart*, which depicts the traditional Igbo society and its early encounters with colonialism, conforms to Genette's notion of folklore narrative which "habitually conforms, at least in its major articulations, to chronological order" (Genette 36). To the contrary, *No Longer at Ease*, which depicts pre-independence Nigerian society, conforms more to the Western "literary tradition [that] was inaugurated by a characteristic effect of anachrony" (Genette 36).

3. Frequency

Genette defines *frequency*, or simply *repetition*, as the number of times a certain event is narrated in the narrative discourse (Genette 113). For example, repetition is a key element in the embedded miniature narrative of Abame village that is mentioned in both *Things Fall Apart* and *Arrow of God*. The complete story of how Abame village was completely wiped out by the colonizers is mentioned in *Things Fall Apart*; it is narrated by Obierika to Okonkwo while he was in exile and to his uncle Uchendo. The white man's bicycle, "the 'iron horse' is repeated five times in the story and the killing of the white man as many times ..." (Obiechina, Narrative Proverbs 136), which is very significant since Obiechina contends that "repetition is a mode of deploying emphases in oral narrative and performance" (Narrative Proverbs 136). Repetition here is intended to stress the Igbo people's utter amazement at the white man's appearance and equipment. Repetition in this story is significant particularly when the reader knows later that a whole village was wiped out as a reaction to the killing of a single white man.

What is significant about Achebe's fiction is that the element of frequency could be applied to all three novels as if they were a unified whole. In other words, a certain narrative segment could be spotted in two or even all three novels. For instance, the story of Abame is presented in *Things Fall Apart* five times: [137; ch.15] [144; ch.16] [175-6; ch.20] [192; ch.23] [196; ch.23]. The impact of the story of Abame reaches Ezeulu's village as it is mentioned in *Arrow of God* four times: [27; ch.2] [48; ch.4] [86; ch.8] [132; ch.12].

The frequent reference to what happened to Abame has two aims: the first is to show the terrifying influence of the story and how the spread of one single story about the strength of the colonizers managed to scare the Ibos of both Okonkwo's and Ezeulu's villages, and surely many more: "The white man, Wintabota, brought soldiers to Umuaro and stopped [the war]. The story of what these soldiers did in Abame was still told with fear, and so Umuaro made no effort to resist but laid down their arms" (AG 29; ch.2). The second aim for the repetitive mention of Abame story in two of Achebe's novels is to "suggest the continuity of Achebe's exploration of the theme he introduced in *Things Fall Apart*" (Killam 62).

In *Arrow of God*, the idea that Ezeulu is responsible for sending his son Oduche to join the church is repeated for more than five times. This is meant to show how Ezeulu's arrogance and stubbornness are responsible for his own and his people's downfall. He insists that he "can see things where other men are blind" (AG 133; ch.12), so he decides to send Oduche to join the church against the wish of everyone around him. Although Ezeulu "did not ignore the religious implications of Oduche's act" (AG 62; ch.6) of trying to kill the sacred python, he still insists that Oduche should go to church: "I have said that he will go there and he will go. If anybody does not like it he can come and jump on my back" (AG 62; ch.6). Achebe also mentions more than once that it was the white man, Winterbottom, who has advised Ezeulu in the first place to send one of his sons to be educated at the white man's school. That said Achebe uses frequency here to highlight the art of persuasion as one of the tools of colonialism.

4. Conclusions

A careful examination of Achebe's narrative strategies, one notes that in terms of narrative order both *Things Fall Apart* and *Arrow of God* conform to the chronological order of the story, with a few analeptic narrative segments meant to offer explanations when required or to fill in the gaps in the main story. In this sense, the two novels could be described as folklore narratives according to Genette who maintains that "folklore narrative habitually conforms, at least in its major articulations, to chronological order" (36). In contrast, Achebe employs unconventional narrative strategies in *No Longer at Ease* where the narrative time leaps back and forward in a confusing manner. By doing so, Achebe adopts the "(Western) literary tradition ... [which] was inaugurated by a characteristic effect of anachrony" (Genette 36). Obviously, Achebe presents his first novel in particular as a traditional folktale to establish an African oral tradition distinguishable from the Western tradition.

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